

TYPES OF BUSINESS CORRESPONDENCE AND THEIR STUDY

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Abstract: This thesis deals with the types of business correspondence and their study. It helps to understand the study, structure, composition and lexical features of business correspondence texts.

Keywords: Business letters, correspondence, commercial letters, e-mails, functional purposes.

INTRODUCTUION

In the modern business world, business correspondence is an important part of success. Employees of any organizations come face every day to compile their business correspondence and respond to visitors.

Business letters (business correspondence) are the most common type of documents used for correspondence with a wide range of documents of the enterprise (organisations,institutions). This applies to a single issue (or several issues that are closely related to each other) and allows for the rapid exchange of information between enterprise (organisations,institutions), their structural units (officials), intended short (usually no more than one or two pages) document.

MAIN PART.

When you start to study the peculiarities of the preparation of business letters (business correspondence), it is necessary to mention is the diversity of their types. It should be noted that there are many criteria for the classification of business letters.

In turn, official and private business letters can be further classified according to the specifics of their functional purpose.

It is known that all information documents on which management decisions are made are conditionally divided into reference, informative and reference-analytical.

Reference documents include, first of all, business records, correspondence, protocols, proposals, and presentations.

Correspondence is a generic name for documents of various contents, such as business letters, telegrams, telephone messages, fax messages, email, and so on. Correspondence is used to communicate information between organizations, both in subordinated communication and externally.

In particular, business correspondence is characterized by the largest type of management documents-business letters. Business letters are all documents

that serve to link this organization with external structures. Even if an oral agreement is reached, confirmation of it in a working letter is a guarantee that it will be fulfilled by the business partner.

Thus, the following should be noted in the group of official business letters:

- letters of request;
- message letters;
- inquire letters;
- application letters;
- confirmation letters.

According to the subject, business letters are divided into relevant business and business letters.

1. Commercial letters- used in organizations, conclusion and execution of trade agreements. Commercial letters are written on behalf of legal entities and are often legally binding. Trade correspondence includes commercial inquiries, proposals, letters of demand (complaints) and responses to these letters, letters of credit (when concluding contracts with foreign partners).

2. In fact, business letters address organizational, legal issues, economic relations problems of correspondence, so they are very diverse in form and content. This could be a receipt, an invitation, a meeting minutes, and so on.

According to the function performed, business letters are divided into letters-responses and letters of initiative. Initiative letters, in turn, are divided into:

- Letters demanding a response (letter of business initiative, letter of inquiry, letter of invitation, letter of complaint, letter of appeal);
- Non-reply letters (note letter, warning letter, message letters, statement letter, attachment letter).
- Depending on the recipient, business letters can be divided into regular and round:
 - Letters are regularly sent to one recipient;
 - Round letters are letters sent by one addressee to several recipients, as a rule, to subordinate instance.

One-sided letters solve a single problem. Such letters are preferable. If you need to contact the organization on several unrelated issues at the same time, you will need to write a separate letter for each of them.

Multi-dimensional correspondence is created when it raises several interrelated issues that are considered in the same organization (a single addressee). For example, it could be an invitation letter or a reminder letter.

Work letters by submission from are divided into:

- Traditional postal items (usually letters that have legal force: contracts, offers,

complaints);

- E-mails and faxes (used when there is an urgent need to solve a problem but they have no legal force).

Each work letter falls into several classification and is therefore structured taking into account different aspects. For example, a business inquire letter is active in its function, customers in its addressee, and may be one-sided or multifaceted in content, often regulated in structure.

To study the essence of the matter is to gather enough information. If necessary- to study the legislation on the essence of the publication, to analyze previous appeals on this issue and get answers to them.

The text of the working letter should consist of an appeal, an introductory part, a main part and a conclusion.

Introduction. In the introductory part, indicate the reasons, basics, purposes of creating the document. They are often accompanied by dates, facts, references to documents.

The main part. The main part of the text varies depending on its specific type, as it forms the main purpose of the letter.

CONCLUSION

The concluding part of the letter usually consists of courtesy formulas: "We hope our request is fulfilled", " We look forward to future cooperation", " We wish you success", "We urge you not to delay your answer", "We ask you to forgive us for being late in answering (for a mistake)".

The body of the letter can generally hold one to three written pages. It is recommended to pay special attention to grammar, sentence length (not more than 20 words), and clarity of meaning when composing the text.

The conclusion of this article is that the types of the business correspondence listed above are required to be written in their proper place and in full compliance with the rules. Such correspondence is usually formalized between certain institutions.

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